

A preliminary assessment on CodeMeta support for FAIR and quality characteristics for Research Software

Deliverable D2.5 “Quality criteria and metadata” for nfdi.software NFDI Base project

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Abstract. Here we present our assessment on how CodeMeta aligns with and supports FAIR and quality indicators for research software. We first used a spreadsheet with CodeMeta as a reference point, assessing its support, property by property, to the FAIR for Research Software principles. We then built on top of the work done by the EOSC Task Force Ensure Software Quality, where the FAIR4RS principles were compared against software quality characteristics, adding an alignment to Codemeta properties.

Keywords. Research software, metadata, FAIR4RS, software quality

Motivation

Various initiatives around good practices for research software, e.g., FAIR principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS) [1], software management plans (SMPs) [2,3] and [CodeMeta](#) [4] recognized the importance of machine-readable (semantically structured) metadata as it provides a quick overview that can also be combined with other research artifacts, e.g., the data transformed by a software. Software quality characteristics complement the picture. Aligning such efforts, in particular FAIR4RS, quality characteristics and CodeMeta, would contribute to improve the overall reusability of research software.

Within the scope of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) in Germany, the NFDI4Base project nfdi.software aims at providing a registry for research software, enriched with metadata aligned to FAIR4RS, boosting good practices and good quality for research software. Here we report on the nfdi.software assessment on how CodeMeta properties support

FAIR4RS principles and some quality indicators. Our work builds on top of the alignment between FAIR4RS and software quality characteristics carried out by the EOSC Task Force Ensure Software Quality [5]. This assessment corresponds to the deliverable D2.5 of the initialization phase [6].

Approach

Alignment between CodeMeta and FARI4RS. We used a spreadsheet with CodeMeta as a reference point, for each CodeMeta property, we added columns for each FAIR4RS principle (F, A, I, and R). Two people discussed together and added their opinion on which sub-principle would be supported by a property and the reasoning behind. Two more people acted as reviewers and went independently through the initial alignment and provided feedback, which was later incorporated in the final alignment presented here.

Alignment between FAIR4RS, quality characteristics, and CodeMeta. Based on the initial alignment between FAIR4RS and quality indicators [5] and the alignment between CodeMeta and FAIR4RS from the previous step, we summarized how the quality characteristics are supported by properties in CodeMeta.

Results

Alignment between CodeMeta and FARI4RS. Some FAIR4RS principles rely not on the software itself but on external resources. As CodeMeta properties mostly describe the software itself, there are some FAIR4RS principles that cannot be fully covered by software metadata, those are:

- *F4. Metadata are FAIR, searchable and indexable.* Thanks to the use of CodeMeta (combined with other efforts around permanent identifiers), software metadata indeed becomes FAIR; however, for the metadata to be searchable and indexable it is needed to make it available in a software registry which actually exposes the metadata for humans and machines to access it and use it
- *A1. Software is retrievable by its identifier using a standardised communications protocol.* An identifier (indeed covered by metadata) is needed but its retrievability depends on the protocol rather than the metadata
- *A1.1. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.* Again, this principle is about the communication protocol used to retrieve and access the software.
- *I1. Software reads, writes and exchanges data in a way that meets domain-relevant community standards.* This principle refers more to the data and community agreements that the software itself. The software metadata can provide a link to datasets used as input or produced as output but describing the data formats and standards would be part of the metadata for the data rather than the software. Community agreements can be added in the form of validators for the software and data metadata but that corresponds to a resource outside the metadata scope.

- *R3. Software meets domain-relevant community standards.* This is again about community agreements. They relate to metadata in the sense that a community can recommend some metadata schema, e.g., CodeMeta; in this sense, it could be possible to argue that by using CodeMeta R3 is, at least, partially covered.

In addition, the principle “*F1.1. Components of the software representing levels of granularity are assigned distinct identifiers*” was not aligned to any CodeMeta property as we found that components are not well identified and covered by CodeMeta. While the principle “*F2. Software is described with rich metadata*” was aligned to every CodeMeta property as it is directly about metadata descriptors (which is the purpose of CodeMeta, describing software with metadata).

There was no agreement on four properties as at least one of the reviewers suggested additional alignments:

- *applicationCategory, defined as “Type of software application, e.g. ‘Game, Multimedia’”.* A reviewer considers that it could be useful for reusability (R1) but no clear example was found on how “game” or “multimedia” (or similar) could be useful to assess reusability.
- *applicationSubCategory, defined as “Subcategory of the application, e.g. ‘Arcade Game’”.* A reviewer considers that it could be useful for reusability (R1) but no clear example was found on how “arcade game” (or similar) could be useful to assess reusability.
- *editor, defined as “Specifies the Person who edited the CreativeWork”.* One of the reviewers considers that a software editor would be in charge of curation, documentation or releases so providing additional information about the provenance of the software (R1.2). However, there is no evidence it has been used as such in CodeMeta as no further description or examples are provided. In addition, linking to the editor would not give access to the changes made by the editor.
- *fileSize defined as “Size of the application / package (e.g. 18MB). In the absence of a unit (MB, KB etc.), KB will be assumed”.* One of the reviewers considers the size of the software in the form of a file (e.g., zip or tar size) could provide additional information for researchers to judge reusability (R1). However, even if the file size indicates that the software can be, for instance, locally downloaded (as there is enough space in the local disk), it does not mean that it can be actually (re)used as there is an additional process needed to get access to the software (e.g., unzip or install).

Further alignment for all the 62 CodeMeta properties to describe software is presented in the annexed table “CodeMeta and FAIR4RS alignment”, provided as Excel, ODP, and CSV. We found that F and R principles are well represented by metadata while I is almost not covered at all.

Alignment between FAIR4RS, quality characteristics, and CodeMeta. We used the existing alignment between FAIR4RS and quality characteristics and added a new column with information about the related CodeMeta properties and the reasoning behind. Both reviewers agreed with the information provided in the table except for two quality characteristics as detailed below:

- *EOSC-Qual-26 (compliance to development standards)*. One of the reviewers considers that development standards could be reflected in properties such as "fileFormat", "programmingLanguages", "softwareRequirements", "runtimePlatform".
- *EOSC-SWRelMan-12 (packaging, installability)*. One of the reviewers considers that "developmentStatus" also relates to packaging and installability.

The alignment table is presented below, with the two first columns coming from an EOSC report on software quality characteristics [5]. We used colors to help visual understanding of the table. Red indicates that we did not find any CodeMeta property that aligns to the quality characteristic, yellow partial alignment, and green good alignment. The alignment levels are also mentioned as text in the fourth column to make it easier for printing or data-processing. As observed in the table, out of 36 quality characteristics, for 21 (~58%) we did not find an alignment to metadata, for 10 (~28%) there was a partial alignment, and for 5 (~14%) there was a good alignment. Metadata support can be improved by extended schemas such as the machine-actionable Software Management Plan (maSMP, types [7] and recommendations of use [8]) as SMPs cover some additional aspects also considered in the quality characteristics. Please notice that no quality characteristic was aligned to A1 by the ESOC Task Force, so it appears blank in the table. The table is also provided as an annexed Table "FAIR4RS, Quality and CodeMeta alignment", as Excel, ODP, and CSV.

Table 1. Alignment between FAIR4RS, quality characteristics, and CodeMeta.

FAIR4RS principle	Quality characteristic	Comment	Alignment
F1 - PID	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code. Also, CodeMeta metadata commonly refers to external metadata, outside the code.	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-13 (built sw in repo/registry)	installUrl is related to a built version of the sw somewhere else but PID for it would not be part of sw metadata. SMPs considered the registry where the sw is deposited	Partial alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-25 (provide checksums)	No checksums covered in metadata	No alignment
F1.1 - PID for components	EOSC-SWRelMan-05 (use of branches)	No metadata property related to branches	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-33 (documentation has a PID)	Documentation could be reached from softwareHelp but from the sw metadata it is not possible to know whether it will have a PID	Partial alignment
F1.2 - PID for versions	EOSC-SWRelMan-02 (use of version control system)	No metadata related to version control systems, it is considered in SMPs	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-04 (main	No metadata related to branches or their	No

	branch is the working version)	roles in the development cycle	alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-06 (branch for next release)	No metadata related to branches or their roles in the development cycle	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-09 (use of semantic versioning)	softwareVersion is included but no requirement for it to be semantic versioning. In this case, softwareVersion is probably more aligned than version (provided at CreativeWork level) . This could be covered with a profile, it is also considered in SMPs.	Partial alignment
F2 - Rich metadata	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-26 (documentation version controlled)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether any documentation is versioned controlled	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-29 (documentation online)	If softwareHelp is interpreted as documentation for the sw, it is covered (online is probably a good guess).	Good alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-30 (documentation is updated with new versions)	Not possible to identify updates on the documentation, less whether they are aligned to new versions	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-31 (documentation updated if unclear/inaccurate)	Not possible to identify it from the metadata	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-32 (documentation aligns to target audience)	Not possible to identify it from the metadata. SMPs consider different kinds of documentation.	No alignment
	EOSC-Qual-24 (intellectual property described via rights, usage restrictions, authors and citation)	isAccessibleForFree and license are related to usage restrictions and permissions, author and citation properties also support this quality attribute	Good alignment
F3 - Metadata includes PID	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code	No alignment
F4 - Metadata is FAIR, searchable and indexed	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code	No alignment
A1 - Retrievable by PID			
A1.1 - Protocol open, free, universal	EOSC-SWRelMan-01 (open-source code)	codeRepository fulfills this quality indicator but it was aligned to R1 rather than A1.1	Good alignment

A1.2 - Protocol allows authentication	EOSC-SWTest-18 (authentication and authorization used in the sw)	The metadata does not include properties related to authentication or authorization mechanisms supported by the sw	No alignment
A2 - Metadata always accessible	EOSC-SWRelMan-13 (built sw in repo/registry)	installUrl is related to a built version of the sw somewhere; however, it is not possible to know what metadata will be included in the repo/registry. In addition, currently there is no property in CodeMeta that would point to a registry (either for the source code or an executable)	Partial alignment
I1 - Data exchange aligned to communities	EOSC-Qual-26 (compliance to development standards) Note: in the EOSC report it appears at EOSC-Qual-29 which does not exist. We think it is 26 based on the rationale used for the mapping between FAIR4RS and quality attributes	From the metadata, it is not possible to know which standards were used for the data used/processed by the sw.	No alignment
	EOSC-SWTest-01 (code style)	Not possible to judge from the metadata. SMPs include some testing that could relate to code styling	No alignment
I2 - Reference to other objects	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code	No alignment
R1 - Relevant attributes	EOSC-SWRelMan-11 (metadata included in code)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether it is included in the code	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-29 (documentation online)	If softwareHelp is interpreted as documentation for the sw, it is covered (online is probably a good guess).	Good alignment
R1.1 - License	EOSC-SWRelMan-10 (open-source license)	license is the corresponding property but there is not guarantee it will be an open-source license	Partial alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-34 (documentation license)	Not possible to identify from metadata whether the documentation has a license but if softwareHelp is used as documentation of the software, as a CreativeWork, it has the potential of including a license	Partial alignment
	EOSC-SrvOps-01 (acceptable usage policy is declared)	license could include some information about acceptable usage but not as a policy. An additional metadata property could be more appropriate for transparency	Partial alignment

	EOSC-SrvOps-02 (access policy and terms of use are declared)	license could include some information about acceptable usage but not as a policy. An additional metadata property could be more appropriate for transparency	Partial alignment
R1.2 - Provenance	EOSC-SWRelMan-29 (documentation online)	If softwareHelp is interpreted as documentation for the sw, it is covered (online is probably a good guess).	Good alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-30 (documentation is updated with new versions)	Not possible to identify updates on the documentation, less whether they are aligned to new versions	No alignment
R2 - References to other sw	EOSC-SWTest-25 (testing to ensure secured services)	The metadata properties do not include information about security testing. This could potentially be covered by SMPs as they include some information about testing	No alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-12 (packaging, installability)	isSourceCodeOf (and targetProduct when used to link to the source-code to its application, also hasSourceCode by symmetry) is related to it although the packaging could be a zip or tar so maybe not ideal for installability.	Partial alignment
R3 - Meets community standards	EOSC-Qual-26 (compliance to development standards) Note: in the EOSC report it appears at EOSC-Qual-29 which does not exist. We think it is 26 based on the rationale used for the mapping between FAIR4RS and QIs	Many metadata properties align to good practices so, if present and of good quality, they would evidence some adherence to development standards. However, it depends more on the quality of the metadata and it is not possible to point to a specific metadata property as many are related to good practices.	Partial alignment
	EOSC-SWRelMan-32 (documentation aligned to target audience)	Not possible to identify it from the metadata. SMPs consider different kinds of documentation.	No alignment

Conclusion

We have presented here a preliminary alignment across FAIR4RS, software quality characteristics, and CodeMeta. This constitutes the first step to further develop an nfdi.software concept for quality at metadata and software levels.

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